

STUDIES ON RANCIDITY OF BUTTERFAT. PART V. THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE

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The induction period of the fat diminishes with temperature, peroxide value increasing with time; at the high temperatures, viz., 105° and 120°, there is enhanced decomposition of the peroxide.

Temperature as a means of speeding up chemical reactions needs no introduction and in common with all other chemical reactions, the rate of development of rancidity in a fat sample exposed to air is increased by raising the temperature. However, it has not been known whether an elevation of temperature would result in a simple, regular and uniform increase in the rate of the reaction. It has been the purpose of this communication to study whether oxidation of butterfat in absence of light and positive catalyst has a normal temperature coefficient. The rate of development of rancidity has been studied at 60°, 85°, 105° and 120° respectively. For this purpose 20 c.c. samples of butterfat were placed in flat glass petri dishes (3" dia.) and were incubated in electrically controlled air-oven. At desired intervals one dish was taken out and peroxide and Kreis measurements were immediately made or as in some cases, the sample was stored in the refrigerator immediately and determinations were made next day. The experimental results are tabulated below.

TABLE I
Kreis and peroxide values of butterfat oxidised at diff. temp.

Temp. = 60°.											
Exposure (hrs.)	1	2	4	5	8	10	12	15	18	20	
Kreis No.	0.2	0.5	0.7	1.0	1.2	1.5	1.7	2.0	3.8	5.0	
Peroxide value	0.5	1.0	1.3	2.0	3.7	5.0	7.5	9.0	12.5	20	
Temp. = 85°.											
Exposure (hrs.)	1	2	4	5	6	8	9	11	12	14	15
Kreis No.	0.5	1.0	1.1	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.7	2.0	2.0	4.4
Peroxide value	0.65	1.2	2.4	3.1	4.0	6.0	7.6	12.0	14.0	1.0	22.0
Temp. = 105°.											
Exposure (hrs.)		1	2	4	5	6	8	10	12		
Kreis No.		1.0	1.1	1.4	2.2	5.3	7.1	16	19.8		
Peroxide value		1.25	3.0	10.0	13.85	18.0	33.5	80.0*	50.0		
Temp. = 120°.											
Exposure (hrs.)		0.5	1	3	5	7	8	9	10		
Kreis No.		1.3	4.7	5.1	7.7	10.4	17.2	17.7	20		
Peroxide value		2.0	4.54	32.5	52.0	115.0*	67.5	62.5	50		

* After this point peroxide decomposition starts.

The peroxide and Kreis values were determined by the methods described previously (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 551).

The rate of development of rancidity at different temperatures is shown graphically in Figures 1-4. It appears from these data that the rate of forma-

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

tion of peroxide steadily increases as the temperature is raised up to 85°, the duration of induction period (taken as the time necessary to reach a peroxide value of 2.0) gradually diminishes. Further increase of temperature causes rapid formation of peroxides, and autoxidation of the fat seems to proceed

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

with little or practically no induction period at temperatures above 100°. Figure 5 shows the peroxide curves at various temperatures on the same abscissa of time and demonstrates more clearly the difference due to temperature. The steepness of the curve steadily increases as the temperature is increased. At higher temperatures decomposition of peroxide also plays an important role as can be seen from Figures 3 and 4. The time to reach a

definite peroxide value (viz. 2.0) progressively diminishes as the temperature is increased and this is illustrated in Table II together with the temperature

FIG. 5

coefficients calculated between various temperature ranges.

TABLE II

Induction period of butterfat at various temperatures.

Temp.	37°	60°	85°	105°	120°
Induction period (hrs.)	1080	5	3	1.5	0.75

TABLE III

Temperature coefficient.

Temp. range	60°—85°	85°—105°	105°—120°
Temp. coeff.	1.65	2.0	2.0

It appears that the induction period of the fat diminishes progressively with the rise of temperature, and the speed of decomposition of peroxides becomes progressively greater as increased oxidation progresses at higher temperatures viz. at 105° and 120°.